

1 Supplementary Information for:

2 **A cryogel-based bioreactor for water treatment applications**

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9 **Summary:** this supplementary information contains 9 figures and 2 tables in 19 pages.

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11 **2. Materials and Methods.**

12 Two known strains of phenol-degrading bacteria *Pseudomonas mendocina* (*P. mendocina* or
13 *Pse*) (NCIMB 13264) and *Rhodococcus koreensis* (*R. koreensis* or *Rho*) (NCIMB 13709) were
14 purchased from the National Collection of Industrial, Food and Marine Bacteria, UK.
15 *Acinetobacter radioresistens* (*A. radioresistens* or *Acn*) was obtained from the culture
16 collection PABS, UoB (Acinetobacter 16S rRNA analysis is given in supplementary
17 information). Tryptone soya broth (TSB), tryptone soya agar (TSA) and phosphate buffered
18 saline (PBS) were obtained from Oxoid Ltd, UK. Live/Dead Bac Light kit (L7007) sodium
19 chloride, phenol, ammonium chloride, Gellan Gum (Gel)(technical grade) were purchased
20 from Fisher Scientific Co, UK. Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) and rhodamine B were
21 purchased from Sigma Aldrich, UK. 4-aminoantipyrine, glutaraldehyde (GA) solution 50 w/v
22 %, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) (deacetylation degree 86.7-88.7%, Mw 67,000 Da),
23 polyethyleneimine, linear (Mw 423 Da), chitosan (CHI) (medium viscosity), Pur-A-Lyzer TM
24 Mega 1000 Dialysis Kit (1000 Da) and (14 kDa) pore size were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.
25 Potassium ferricyanide and ammonium hydroxide (28-30 wt/v % solution of NH₄OH in water)
26 Gellan Gum were obtained from Acros Organics, UK.

27 2.1 *Acinetobacter* 16S rRNA analysis

28 The presumptive *Acinetobacter* isolates were characterised biochemically by Gram
29 staining, growth on differential and enriched media, the oxidase test, the catalase test, the
30 motility test,(MacFaddin et al., 2000 and 2000) the Phenylalanine Deaminase test,(MacFaddin
31 et al., 2000) and with API 20E and API 20NE kits (BioMerieux, France). Isolates identified as
32 presumptive *Acinetobacter* species were further identified using 16S rRNA analysis.

33 Molecular identification was performed via the polymerase chain reaction (PCR), using
34 the 16S rRNA universal primers (27F: 5'-AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG-3' and 1492R: 5'-
35 ACCTTGTTACGACTT-3') for DNA amplification.(Weisburg et al., 1991; Jiang et.al 2013)
36 DNeasy TM Blood & Tissue kit (Qiagen, UK) was used to extract and purify DNA following
37 the manufacturer's instructions. The extracted DNA was diluted with biologically sterilised
38 water at a ratio of 1:10 and mixed using a Mega Mix- Royal solution kit (Microzone, UK),
39 containing Taq polymerase, 2x enhancing buffer (6 mM MgCl₂) with 400 μM dNTPs and blue
40 MiZN loading dye and stabiliser, prior to PCR. The stock DNA extractions were stored at -
41 20oC for further use.

42 A 12.5μl volume of Mega Mix- Royal solution was added to an equal volume of DNA,
43 primer and water to give 25 μl total volume to activate the tag polymerase. Following initial
44 denaturation at 95°C for 5 minutes the PCR thermocycler (G-Storm, LabTech International,
45 UK) was run for 30 cycles of 95°C for 1 minute, 50°C for 45 seconds, with extension at 72°C
46 for 1.5 minutes and a final extension of 72°C for 10 minutes.

47 Separation and visualisation of the amplified DNA fragments was achieved through
48 agarose gel electrophoresis of 10 μl of amplification products with an agarose concentration of
49 1.5% agarose. A size ladder up to 4500pb was used with distilled water as a control, with
50 electrophoresed Tris-Acetic-EDTA (TAE) buffer for three hours at 100 volts on a HU15
51 horizontal gel units (LabTech International, UK).

52 After electrophoresis the gels were stained using ethidium bromide at a concentration
53 0.5% for 15 minutes then, after washing in water, imaged and documented using the SynGene
54 programme and SynGene INGENIUS UV imager(Fig. S1). Identification of DNA sequences
55 was performed on 25 µl aliquots of amplification products at a concentration of 20ng/µl by the
56 Eurofins Genomics DNA sequencing service.

57 The API20NE biochemical identification was confirmed by comparison of the identity code
58 (0000032) with the API database online; this resulted in a 96.7% similarity to *Acinetobacter*
59 *radioresistens*.

60 The result of 16s rRNA sequences of *Acinetobacter radioresistens* were compared with
61 those in the Genebank database through BLAST analysis, using the Greengenes website
62 (http://greengenes.lbl.gov/cgi-bin/JD_Tutorial/nph-16S.cgi). From this the identity of the
63 presumptive phenol-degrading *Acinetobacter* isolates were identified as *Acinetobacter*
64 *radioresistens* strains SK82 at a probability of 99.80% and 100% for the forward and reverse
65 primers.

66 2.2 Estimation of toxicity of cross-linking polymers.

67 Cultured media (80 mL) was centrifuged at 10 000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. The obtained
68 pellet was re-suspended in PBS buffer. The 0.5 mL suspension of bacteria in PBS buffer was
69 used as a positive control. 0.5 mL of the suspension was mixed with PEI-al, PVA-al, and PVA
70 polymers, and a combination PEI-al & PVA-al. GA (0.25 and 0.5 v/v %) was used as a negative
71 control. Part of the samples were kept at 4 °C for 24h, while the other part of the same
72 composition solution was frozen at -12 °C and kept frozen for 24h. Then, the frozen samples
73 were defrosted at room temperature and the number of live bacteria estimated using MTT
74 assay.

75 The viability of cross-linked bacteria within the cryogel structure was evaluated using
76 the LIVE/DEAD® bacterial viability kit and confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM, Leica
77 TCS SP5). Hydrogel-Rho-Gellan0.5% Hydrogel-Rho-Gellan(1.0%) and Cryo-Rho-

78 Gellan(0.5%) PVAal (0.3%) cryogels were cut into slices with thickness of 1 mm. The samples
79 were rinsed twice with 0.9% NaCl buffer and stained with SYTO 9 stain (wavelength 480/500
80 nm) and propidium iodide (wavelength 490/635 nm) for 15 minutes at room temperature under
81 dark conditions according to the protocol of the LIVE/DEAD ® Bacterial viability kit.

82 2.3 Monitoring of phenol derivative concentration

83 For assessment of phenol, m-cresol, 2-CP and 4-CP concentration, samples of 100 µL
84 volume were transferred into an eppendorf tube (1.5 mL) and diluted with water (0.8 mL). Fifty
85 µL of ammonium buffer was added to adjust pH to ten. 4-aminoantipyrine (25 µL, 20 mg/mL)
86 solution followed by 25 µL potassium ferricyanide (0.242 mol/L) was added. The mixtures
87 were vortexed and centrifuged at 13 000 rpm and absorbance at 510 nm was measured. The
88 final concentrations of phenol derivatives and their possible by-products in water after
89 degradation by the 3D, cryostructured, macroporous bioreactors (henceforth termed
90 cryobacteria reactors, or CBRs) were estimated using an Agilent 1100 HPLC. All samples were
91 diluted 1:1 with HPLC grade methanol and frozen at -20 °C for 2-3h to precipitate unwanted
92 compounds. Samples were centrifuged at 10 000 rpm for five minutes and filtered through
93 0.22-µm filter membranes before HPLC analysis using a UV detector at 280 nm. A reverse
94 phase column C18 was used, and the flow rate of the mobile phase was 1 mL/min.

95 HPLC method. Mobile phase Acetic acid 1 % v/v in water (C) and methanol (D) was
96 used. Column and sample temperatures were 45 °C and 25 °C, respectively; C) gradient start
97 at 75.0, End at 44.0 %; D) gradient start at 25.0, end at 56.0 % for 9.5 min, and at composition
98 44 % - 56 % C-D for 5 min; C) gradient start at 44.0, end at 0 % with duration of 1.0 min and
99 D) gradient start at 56.0 %, end at 100.0 %, for 1.0 min. 5 minutes at 100 % of CH₃OH & 1 %
100 HAc. C) gradient start at 0, end at 75.0 % for 1.0 min; D) gradient start at 100.0, end at 25.0 %
101 with duration of 1.0 min. Retention time (min) used: phenol (5.58-6.6), p-cresol (8.88), m-
102 cresol (8.99), p-hydroxybenzoic acid (3.4), hydroquinone (1.97), protocatechuate (2.396), 2-
103 chlorophenol (9.44), 4-chlorophenol(10.75).

3. Results

105

106 **Fig. S1.** Electrophoresis of 16S rRNA *Acinetobacter* unknown(Gramm negative,
107 coccus/coccobacillus, oxidise negative, catalase positive, non-fermentative) and comparison
108 with *Acinetobacter radioresistence*.

110

111 **Fig. S2.** H-NMR-spectra recorded in D₂O of: a) glutaraldehyde, b) PEI, c) PEI-al, d) PVA-al,
 112 e) PVA.

113

114 **Characterisation of new polymers and morphology of materials**

115 A group of multiplets in the range of 3.55-3.70 ppm in the spectra (Fig. S1a) corresponds to
 116 backbone protons of PEI, which shifted after the modification of the polymer. The
 117 condensation reaction of the primary and secondary amino groups of PEI with GA leads to the
 118 disappearance of amine functionality at 2.6 ppm (Fig. S1b). The backbone protons of GA

119 moiety appeared at 1.25-1.75 ppm and in the field of 5ppm attributed to hemiacetal form of
 120 GA (Fig. S1d)(Wang et al. 2014). Aldehyde groups were observed at 9.6 ppm (Fig. S1a). The
 121 proton of Schiff's base in the ¹H-NMR spectrum of PEI-al appeared at 8.36 ppm (Ederer et al.,
 122 2007; Boghaei et al., 2008; Makhubela et al., 2011). PVA-al has two additional signals at 7.7
 123 and 6.3 ppm which are attributed to presence of protons of the cyclic acetal form and multiplets
 124 at 2.23 ppm related to glutaraldehyde moieties(CH₂(4H)) and the singlets at 2.1ppm attributed
 125 to acethyl groups(CH₃) of PVA (Fig. S1c). Taking into account the relation of integrals of
 126 peaks for backbone -(CH₂-CH(R))_n- of PVA at 1.6ppm and the characteristic signal of
 127 glutaraldehyde (CH₂(4H)) one can conclude that the ration between structural unit of PVA to
 128 GA was 14.8 : 1(Fig. S1c). FTIR spectra of PEI-al and PVA-al showed carbonyl groups at
 129 1714 cm⁻¹ and 1717 cm⁻¹, respectively, which indicated the presence of free aldehyde groups
 130 in the polymer structure.

131

132

133 **Fig. S3.** Hydrodynamic weight distribution of polymers: a & b) PEI-al; c & d) PVA; e & f)
 134 PVA-al. Zeta potential of polymers in water: g) PEI-al; h) PVA-al.
 135
 136 The concentration of aldehyde groups in PVA-al was estimated using a known reaction with
 137 hydroxylamine and subsequent titration of released hydrochloric acid(Zhao et al., 1991).
 138 Thus, the 2% PVA-al solution contained 6.25 mM/L of aldehyde groups, while the 1% PEI-al
 139 solution contained approximately 57 mM/L of aldehyde groups, calculated via measuring the
 140 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine assay, which was used previously for estimation of amount of
 141 aldehyde groups in oxidised dextran(Berillo et al. 2012). PVA-al and PEI-al contained 0.3125
 142 mM/g_{dry polymer} and 5.7 mM/g_{dry polymer} of aldehyde groups, respectively.

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144

145 **Fig. S4.** Plot of elastic properties of composite cryogels based on *Rhodococcus korensis*
 146 using different polymer compositions and cross-linking agents.

147

148 **Table S1.** Evaluation of toxicity of polymers at different compositions and temperature, prior
 149 to MTT assay incubation of bacteria (at 4 °C for 24h, otherwise specified) of polymers with
 150 PVA-al and PEI-al 0.6:0.6% (1:1).

Sample name	% of viable cells	Number of viable cells, CFU xE6
Pse & PBS (positive control)	50.0	62.5±1.4
Pse & PBS and 2% glucose.	43.0	53.9±1.15
Cryo-Pse-PEI-al:PVA-al-glucose 0.6:0.6:2.0(%); -12°C	13.7	17.2±5.4
Cryo-Pse-PEI-al:PVA-al 0.6:0.6(%); -12°C	12.0	15.0±0.25
Pse & PEI-al:PVAal 0.6:0.6(%)	34.4	43.2±5.4
Pse & PEI-al:PVA-al-glucose 0.6:0.6:2.0(%)	32.6	40.9±4.58
Pse & PBS initial (positive control)	100.0	125.53±2.8
Pse & PBS and 2% glucose initial	86.2	108.25±2.3
Rho & PBS (positive control)	100.0	802±15
Rho & PEI-al:PVA-al 0.6:0.6% and 0.9% NaCl	96.2	772.3±41
Rho & PVA-al 2.4%	76.5	613.8±14
Rho & PVA-al 3%	72.4	581±7
Rho & PEI 1.0% GA 0.5%(6000 CFU initially)	20.3	163±3.4
Rho & 0.5% GA in PBS (6000 CFU initially)	17.1	137.4 ±5
Acn & PEI-al 3%	75.2	44.6 ±1.1
Acn & PVA-al 2.4%	69.5	41.2 ±0.41
Acn & PEI 1% PBS	49.7	29.5 ±0.86
Acn & PEI 1% PBS 0.25% GA	13.7	8.12 ±0.15
Acn & GA 0.25% PBS negative control	7.6	4.54 ±0.22
Acn & PBS buffer positive control	100.0	59.3 ±1.2
Acn & PEI-al 0.365%	25.12	14.9 ±0.3
Acn & PVA-al 1.2%	92.4	54.8 ±0.23

Acn & PEI-al 0.5% PBS	13.8	8.2 ±0.2
Cryo-Acn-PEI-al-PVA-al 0.6:0.6%; -12C	24.3	14.4 ±1.9
Cryo-Acn-PEI-al-PVA-al-glucose 0.6:0.5:2.0%; -12C	17.4	10.3 ±0.74
Cryo-Acn-PVA-al-glucose 1.2:2.0(%) PBS; -12C	109.1	64.7 ±0.97
Acn & PVA-al-glucose 1.2:2.0%, PBS	54.13	32.1±7.9
Acn & PEI-al: PVA-al0.6:0.6%, PBS	44.5	26.4±0.9

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153 **Fig. S5.** Degradation of phenol by: **A)** CBR-*Acn*, **B)** CBR-*Pse*, **C)** CBR-*Rho* (2 plastic
 154 carriers ($12.2 \pm 3.6 \times 10^6$ CFU) per each bottle V 200 mL; 54 ppm for 10 cycles, (n=3).
 155 **D)** Control experiment bioremediation of phenol(50ppm) in presence of suspension of
 156 bacteria *Pseudomonas mendocina* (\blacktriangle), *Rhodococcus korensis* (x), solution of phenol without
 157 bacteria(\blacklozenge), for 1st cycle (amount of bacteria comparable to amount of bacteria used in
 158 cryogels)(n=2).

159
 160 **Fig. S6.** Degradation of phenol in MSM vs time by: CBR-*Pse* ($38 \pm 8.3 \times 10^6$ CFU)(●); CBR-
 161 *Rho* ($576 \pm 52 \times 10^6$ CFU)(◇); CBR-*Acn* ($17.6 \pm 0.96 \times 10^6$ CFU)(□), for 5th cycle, 2 plastic carriers
 162 per bottle V 200 mL, 280ppm phenol;

163

164

165 **Fig. S7.** Dynamics of change of viable bacteria of *Pse* (blue and green) and *Rho* (red and
 166 violet) in the 50 ppm 4-CP solution in a dynamic mode (shaking at 150 rpm) in buffer: A) 25
 167 mM carbonate buffer; B) in MSM, (n=3).

168 **Table S2.** Concentration of 4-CP estimated using HPLC after the bioremediation period.

169 Initial concentration of the 4-CP was 62 ppm, volume 40 mL.

Name of the sample	Remaining phenol after one month bioremediation, ppm	remaining phenol from initial, %
<i>Rho</i> suspension, MSM buffer	45.2	72.9
Control PEI-al-PVA-al cryogel (no bacteria) MSM buffer	59.0	95.1
Control PVA-al cryogel (no bacteria) MSM buffer	61.31	98.9
Cryogel <i>Pse</i> PVA-al PEI-al 0.5% 0.6% MSM	34.84	56.2
Cryogel <i>Pse</i> PVA-al PEI-al 1.0%: 0.25% MSM	31.85	51.3
Cryogel <i>Pse</i> PVA-al 1% MSM buffer	25.95	41.8
<i>Rho</i> suspension, carbonate buffer	59.26	95.5
<i>Rho</i> suspension, carbonate buffer	61.07	98.3
<i>Rho</i> suspension, carbonate buffer	59.63	96.2
<i>Pse</i> suspension(commercial) carbonate buffer	55.76	89.9

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173 **Fig. S8.** Degradation of 4-CP (V 40 ml, 50 ppm) in MSM by suspension of free *Pse* 4-CP
 174 adapted (□), *Rho* 4-CP adapted (○) vs time in a dynamic mode (shaking at 150 rpm), number
 175 of cell 0.6×10^8 per sample (n=2), concentration estimated using aminoantipyrine assay.

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180 **Fig. S9.** Dynamics of change of the population of free bacteria during the bioremediation
181 process in a dynamic mode (shaking 150 rpm) : A) 50ppm of 4-CP solution in MSM;
182 B) nonadapted on the agar plate, cultivated suspension *Rho* in MSM: 2-CP 60 ppm (▲); 2-
183 CP 20 ppm (■); 4-CP 10 ppm (◆) (n=3). C) *Rho* adapted to CP 25 ppm) during the
184 bioremediation process of 2-CP in MSM in a shaking mode (n=2).

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